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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy

D1.3. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Summary

This Data Management Plan (DMP) will contribute to the management of research data collected or generated in the course of InBestSoil work and how these data is going to be stored, published, cited and made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) beyond the project life. Our goal is to meet the requirements of excellent scientific practice and to allow for accessibility, interoperability, reproducibility of InBestSoil research results. This DMP also aims to contribute to the development of the European Soil Observatory (EUSO). To ensure that relevant knowledge and project outputs (including data) are fed to the EUSO, datasets of relevance to the EUSO have been identified.

Deliverable Number	Work Package		
D1.3	WP1		
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(s)		
UVigo	David Fernández-Calviño [UVigo] and Raúl Zornoza (UPCT)		
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Single contact point with EUSO	Data Manager		
Raúl Zornoza (raul.zornoza@upct.es)	Raúl Zornoza		
Type of deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	x
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethycs	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	x
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Table of contents

1. Data summary	4
2. FAIR data	5
3. Other research outputs.....	7
4. Allocation of resources.....	7
5. Data security.....	8
6. Ethics	8

1. Data summary

Data collection is an essential part of the InBestSoil project which aims to co-create a framework for investment in conservation and recovery of soil health, by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem services delivered by a healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentive development. This assessment relies on six lighthouses and three living labs.

On the one hand, data will derive from collection of existing databases, outcomes from previous and ongoing European and national projects and literature review (sources: Zenodo, PubMed, SCOPUS, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, etc.) (re-used data) to i) select benefit transfer methodology for the estimation of non-market values by using a meta-analysis approach (WP3); ii) identify current business models linked to soil health enhancement and select tools more appropriate for the analyses of potential business models (WP4); and iii) horizontal mapping review of existing European, national and regional policy incentives and nudges contributing to preserving and restoring soil health (WP6). These data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx), text files (.txt), Word files (.docx) or EndNote Clarivates files (.enl).

Data corresponding to history of the lighthouses and living labs will be also collected, such as classification of soil, climate, property, crop history, land management and experimental design of the living lab experimental sites (geolocation, plot characteristics, replications, treatment applied, management practices, sampling and analyses) (WP3). These data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx).

We will collect data related stakeholders' information and contacts, gathered in Excel datasets (.xlsx). Owing to the sensitive information related to persons, this information will never become public nor accessible, being used only by project partners for the objective of the project, deleting the file at the end of the project. It will be shared on Teams for internal use only.

New data will derive from soil analyses from samples collected in all lighthouses and living labs in WP3. Selected indicators for key ecosystem services (provision of food, fibre, raw materials or water, climate regulation, water/air purification, soil pollution reduction, nutrient cycling, biodiversity, habitat for organisms, flood regulation and water storage, cultural heritage, cultural identity, recreation, aesthetics, etc) will be measured in each lighthouse and living lab. These data will be integrated in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). WP3 will also produce new DNA sequencing data of soil biological communities (taxonomic), that will be stored in .bam and .fastq files, which can be operated with the open access R software.

Data generated from Life Cycle Assessment and the economic valuation will be gathered in Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx) to identify real economic benefits of conserving high soil health (WP3).

For the analysis of current business models (WP4), the SOLm food system model implemented will provide output data as either .csv or .xlsx formats. The SOLm model is implemented in R. The farm survey raw data will be stored as spreadsheets in either .csv. or .xlsx formats. For data analysis, STATA will be used, where scripts as stored as do-files (.do). Processed farm survey data will be stored with the .dta extension.

For the assessment of new business models for soil health (WP5), (semi-structured) interviews, stakeholders' meetings and focus groups will be organized, with data stored as Excel spreadsheets (.xlsx), .pdf and .docx files. For quantitative research activities for the adoption of new business models, R or STATA software will be used to process data collected, and so output data will be stored as do-files (.do), dta-files (.dta) or Excel files (.xlsx). In all cases, maps or network data will be elaborated to show results, stored as .png or .jpeg.

Carbon farming certification scheme will be analysed (WP6) with the aim to evaluate the possibility to complemented it with indicators that ensure the accountability of soil health results beyond carbon, introducing the supplementary indicators provided by WP3. Financial and economic incentives will be analysed as a part of value proposition (WP6). Data will be stored as .xlsx files.

Overall, the datasets generated by InBestSoil to fulfil its objectives will be diverse but mostly numeric and, to a lesser extent, text as a result of some of the surveys/questionnaires, and images for mapping and network planning. Datasets will mainly consist of observational data (geolocation data, experimental design data, surveys/questionnaires, economic and financial assessment, business models assessment), experimental data captured by field and laboratory equipment (soil properties delivery of ecosystem services) and simulation data (models applied to assess business models performance in WP4).

Regarding the size of the generated data, relatively many datasets will be produced, but none will be overly big, which will allow them to be collected on spreadsheets for easy accessibility.

Data from soil analyses in the different lighthouses and living labs (WP3) will be of interest to feed **EUSO**, with indicators representing physical, chemical and biological characteristics and processes of soils from different land uses and regions. InBestSoil generated data will be useful for researchers in the field of soil health and quality, land managers, public administration and professionals/business sectors in the field of soil management and soil recovery.

2. FAIR data

01. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Due to the fact that the collected datasets will be diverse and belong to different fields, the metadata standard used to describe the dataset will be the Dublin Core Schema, as it is a flexible and commonly used standard and is also the one adopted by the European OpenAIRE repository, which will be used. We will create the Community “InBestSoil” within Zenodo to increase the efficiency when finding the data of this project. The depositors will create the metadata manually when uploading the datasets to Zenodo. Keywords will also be manually added to each dataset uploaded to Zenodo to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential reuse. These keywords will be provided based on the expertise of the depositors, who are familiar with the most commonly used keywords in their field. All datasets will include some tabs or pages with description of data factors and variable names and units.

02. Making data accessible

All datasets supporting publications will be made openly and publicly available on the OpenAire repository Zenodo upon acceptance of the manuscript for publication. For this, the Community “InBestSoil” will be created. Moreover, all datasets generated along the project work plan will be made public three years after completion of the InBestSoil project, regardless of manuscript publication. The repository Zenodo assigns a DOI for persistent identification and citability of the dataset. The Project dataset identification follows the naming: InBestSoil_<WPno>_<serial number of dataset>_<dataset title>_versionnumber(date). Example: InBestSoil_WP3_1_soil indicators_v1(2024-02-06). All datasets will be uploaded to the InBestSoil Community of Zenodo for easy and rapid finding.

Only data gathered by partners outside the project work plan and protected by IPR, or inside the work plan but containing confidential information (e.g. related to personal interviews, stakeholder’s contact information), will be kept closed for privacy reasons.

Data will be shared among members of work packages continuously as they are being generated, by using the InBestSoil Teams library associated to the O365 platform of tools for collaborative work (online platform belonging to beneficiary UPCT). Furthermore, when a dataset turns openly accessible, it will be announced on the web page of the InBestSoil project www.inbestsoil.eu, where a link to the dataset on Zenodo will be available.

The vast majority of the datasets will be made available as spreadsheets (.xlsx format) and to a lesser extent as .txt, .csv, .docx, .enl, .do, .dta, .bam or .fastq (Table 1). Information about the software needed to open these common files will be provided within each dataset or file.

Table 1. Summary of data generated during InBestSoil project life. The WP in which they will be generated and the format of each one are also indicated.

Data	WP	Format
Project stakeholders' information and contacts datasets	WP2	.xlsx
Literature review, databases and outcomes of projects	WP3, WP4, WP6	.xlsx, .txt, .docx, .enl
History of lighthouses and living labs	WP3	.xlsx
Soil health indicators	WP3	.xlsx
Soil DNA sequencing data	WP3	.bam, .fastq
Life Cycle Assessment	WP3	.xlsx
Economic valuation	WP3	.xlsx
Farm surveys	WP4	.csv, .xlsx, .do, .dta
Analysis of current business models (implementation of SOLm model)	WP4	.csv, .xlsx
New business models by interviews, meetings and focus groups	WP5	.xlsx, .pdf, .docx, .do, .dta
Maps of new business models	WP5	.png, .jpeg
Carbon farming indicators	WP6	.xlsx
Financial and economic incentives	WP6	.xlsx

03. Making data interoperable

The depositors will strive to use commonly and internationally used metadata in their field of research, since no widely accepted specific metadata vocabularies exist. Data variable names and units, commonly accepted by the international scientific community and International System of Units, will be used. The vast majority of the datasets will be made available as spreadsheets, .xlsx format, and to a lesser extent as .txt, .csv, .docx, .enl, .do, .dta, .bam or .fastq, so that they can be fully used by potential users.

04. Increase data re-use

The project will make use, in general, of the CC-BY license. The particular license applicable to each dataset, will be decided on an individual basis, though the recommendation will be either CC-BY or CC-BY-SA.

The data will remain re-usable after the end of the project by anyone interested in it, with no access or time restrictions, since the Zenodo repository will be used. Each archived dataset will

have its own permanent repository ID and will be easily accessible. We expect most of the data generated to be made available without restrictions and only datasets subject to IPR and confidentiality issues will be restricted. Where this is going to be the case, agreements will be made based on the individual datasets. Requests for the use of the data by externals will be approved by the project consortium.

Regarding data quality, since all datasets will support publication in peer-reviewed open access journals, the standards of quality (validation of the sample, replication and comparison with results of similar studies) will be met.

New data will be announced on the InBestSoil website and the different profiles in the social media, with links to the page with the dataset on Zenodo. Internally, all partners and EUSO will be informed by email about the availability of new datasets, including the link to Zenodo.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, InBestSoil beneficiaries will also manage other research outputs generated within the workplan of the project, which will be openly accessible, findable and usable (Table 2).

Table 2. Key exploitable results from InBestSoil, with the exploitation strategy to be followed and the protection mechanism.

Partner	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Related WP	Exploitation strategy / Exploitation path	Protection mechanism
UPCT	Toolkit of soil health indicators and total economic value of soil health	WP3	Open licence for end-users to apply the knowledge to assess soil health indicators to further give them a monetary value	CC-BY licence
UPCT	Web-based calculator for the economic value of soil ecosystem services	WP3	Utility model for end-users to apply the process to give a monetary value to their soils	Utility model
CMCC	Policy conditions and catalogues of existing soil health economic and policy incentives	WP6	Science-policy events (e.g. EU Green Week and/or Conference on modelling for policy support)	Report and open access scientific publication
CMCC	Toolbox of incentive schemes for soil health	WP6	Distributed via repositories (e.g. OPPLA , Knowledge4Policy)	Open access database
CMCC	Report on Policy recommendations for soil health protection.	WP6	Distributed standalone and as a part of European assessment reports such as by EFDRR , EEA...	Report and open access scientific publication

4. Allocation of resources

There are no costs associated to the described mechanisms to make the database FAIR and long term preserved since we are using the Zenodo repository. Data files quality will be checked by the data manager who will be also responsible of submit them to Zenodo. The project coordinator has the ultimate responsibility for the data management in the project.

5. Data security

On one hand, the Zenodo repository takes care of security and backup of the deposited data. On the other hand, regarding the data-sharing process involved between partners during research, Teams Online libraries associated to the O365 platform will be used, and data protection services are provided by Microsoft to prevent the loss of data, within the institutional account of UPCT.

6. Ethics

The ethical aspects related to the personal data collected in InBestSoil datasets are addressed in project deliverable D1.1. Ethics principles and guidelines for protection of personal data.

